

Performance and Power Analysis of a 5G UPF Varying the C-States of the Hosting Server

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Abstract—Energy efficiency will be a crucial feature for the next mobile network generations (B5G and 6G). Therefore, in this paper, we have examined power management techniques to minimize the power consumption while not neglecting performance of the most power-hungry 5G Network Function (NF): the User Plane Function (UPF). A classical power management technique has been used herein: the low power idle. It allows power saving caused by putting the CPU to “sleep” (i.e., C_x state) when not in use. Results show that, in most cases the deeper “sleeping” states are enabled, the more power is saved. This is especially true in the highest load scenario in which the power is more than halved as a result. However, results show that special care should be devoted to the enabling/disabling of the “deepest” sleeping state (C_6) since the transitions from it to the active state (C_0) (and vice versa) actually hinder the power savings. Finally, the performance (as in latency) has been also evaluated, results show no packet losses and small latency in all scenarios.

Keywords—B5G, UPF, energy efficiency, low power idle, ACPI.

I. INTRODUCTION

5G [1] has been the first generation of mobile communications to heavily rely on virtualization technologies. Thanks to the maturity level achieved by Network Function Virtualization [2] and Edge Computing [3] by the time 5G was being designed, they became crucial in shaping the service-based design and provide the flexibility and scalability needed to support the diverse requirements expected for 5G. However, while these technologies have been considered intrinsically green, industry and academia have promptly expressed their concerns [4]-[6] that the current paradigm, in which network and computing resources are freely acquired/released in an as-a-Service fashion, is causing a noticeable usage and deployment increase of computing resources, increasing the associated infrastructure OpEx and CapEx, and, consequently, their energy requirements and carbon footprint.

Luckily, driven by global demands and enforced by initiatives such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [7] and the European Green Deal [8], a renewed interest in the sustainability of ICT technologies is finally

rising. In the current context, sustainability is not viewed as mere energy efficiency anymore; instead, a human-centric approach, in which technological advancements are evaluated in the face of value-based considerations and re-prioritization of different environmental, social and economic outcomes [9]. Moreover, since ICT technologies have historically been the key innovation driver of our society, the realization of a sustainable system design can, in turn, boost the sustainability of non-telecom sectors, which can in turn generate a ripple effect on other neighbouring markets.

While the design of the 6G system is still ongoing, an assessment of the most evident shortcomings of its predecessor can be a reasonable starting point for identifying potential enhancements. For instance, the lack of a common framework [10] between the owner of the physical infrastructure and of the applications and network services running on top of said infrastructure has prevented the proper application of the power management schemes natively available in the servers, causing a waste of resources and, consequently, an increase in their carbon footprint and energy requirements..

Herein, we examine the tradeoff between power consumption and performance, under different power management configurations, of the most power-hungry Network Function (NF) of B5G/5G networks: the User Plane Function (UPF). UPF is the only data plane function, and is responsible for the routing and forwarding of data plane packets towards the correct Data Network (DN) (in uplink) or the correct gNodeB (in downlink).

Different UPF implementations exist. It is worth mentioning that they can be deployed either on general-purpose servers or on hardware acceleration devices (e.g., P4 switches). In this paper, we consider the former and we examine the UPF power consumption and performance while applying power management techniques on such general-purpose servers.

Among the most common power management techniques it is worth mentioning Adaptive Rate (AR) and Low Power Idle (LPI). Both of them are based on the Intel Advanced Configuration and Power Interface (ACPI) standard [11]. The

former consists in dynamically vary the frequency and therefore the power and processing capacity of a CPU; the latter forces CPUs to enter “sleeping” states when not processing any task. In this paper, we applied the latter mechanism. The impact of such power management capabilities has already been presented in a number of studies [12]-[14]. Details regarding the two techniques and the motivation of our choice are provided in Section II. Finally, the goal of this article is to study the power consumption and performance of a B5G/5G UPF, while acting on the “sleeping” states of the hosting server. This will impact the overall power consumption and performance. Therefore, our goal is to find the best combination that allows to minimize the power consumption while ensuring a sufficient performance.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the two power management mechanisms: LPI and AR and justifies our choice. Then, in Section III, the UPF and its implementations are presented. Experimental results and setup can be found in Section IV, while conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. THE ADVANCED CONFIGURATION POWER INTERFACE SPECIFICATION

The first support of power management was introduced with the ACPI standard published in 1996. Over time, more energy saving mechanisms were introduced and Hardware (HW) enhancements were made. Each new generation of general-purpose CPUs consumes less power and is more efficient than the previous one.

The ACPI standard introduces two main different power saving mechanisms, namely performance and power states (P_x and C_x states), respectively, which can be individually employed and tuned for each core in the largest part of today's processors.

Regarding the C_x states, the C_0 power state is an active power state where the CPU executes tasks, while C_1 through C_n power states are processor “sleeping” or idle states, where the processor consumes less power. However, as the sleeping power state becomes deeper, the transition between the active (i.e., C_0) and the sleeping state (and vice versa) requires longer time.

While in the C_0 state, ACPI allows the performance of the processor's core to be tuned through P_x state transitions. P_x states allow modifying the operating energy point of a core by altering the working frequency and/or voltage or throttling its

clock. Therefore, they allow saving power while decreasing the performance of a processor.

Thus, by acting on either the transitions of the C_x or the P_x states the two power management mechanisms (LPI and AR respectively) are implemented. In Figure 1 an example of such mechanisms is provided. In detail, four scenarios are depicted: one where no power management techniques are applied, then, two where only LPI and only AR are applied, and finally one where both mechanisms are applied. As shown in Figure 1, on the one hand, LPI allows saving power when the CPUs are not used by going into “sleeping states” while keeping the highest performance (shown in red) when in active state. On the other hand, AR allows to decrease the power consumption also in active state at the drawback of both decreasing the performance and of consuming an active amount of power when the CPU is not processing anything.

In this paper, we choose to exploit only the LPI mechanism in order not to decrease the performance (which would correspond in high delays or packet loss in the 5G network in this case) and to take advantage of the burstiness and seasonality of the mobile traffic through the “sleeping” states.

The hosting server on which we tested the UPF has an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2680 v4 @ 2.40GHz. In particular, this CPU model has 56 logical CPUs which can assume the following 5 C_x states:

1. C_0 : it corresponds to the active state in which the CPU can execute tasks.
2. C_1 : it corresponds to the “lightest” sleeping state. In this state the Core clock is off. The processor is not executing instructions but can return to an executing state almost instantaneously.
3. C_{1E} : it corresponds to an enhanced C_1 state. Herein the latency to return to C_0 is slightly increased, while the power slightly decreases.
4. C_3 : in this state, clocks are stopped and the local caches (L1/L2) of the core is flushed, and the core is powered down.
5. C_6 : it corresponds to the “deepest” sleep state. Herein, in addition to all the actions taken in the previous sleeping states, the shared cache (L3/LLC) of the package is flushed and at the end the package/whole CPU can be (almost) powered down.

A summary of the effects of the above C_x states is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Comparison between LPI and AR mechanisms.

Figure 2. C_x states and their effects [15].

Figure 3. 5G network and its components.

III. THE USER PLANE FUNCTION

5G networks were designed to overcome the “one size fits all” paradigm to support a wide variety of use cases, including classic Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) and Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication (uRLLC). This is possible thanks to a modular design that allows tailoring resources according to the specific requirements of the use case, such as data rate, latency, spectrum efficiency, etc. The 5G network is not immutable and monolithic, but rather it is composed of NFs that can be easily and quickly deployed anywhere. Such NFs are usually deployed in the forms of either Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers.

As shown in Figure 3, the 5G network is composed of the Control Plane, the User Plane and the Access Network. The Control Plane is composed of several NFs and is mainly responsible for user attachment, authentication and PDU sessions management. The User Plane, on which this paper is

focused, is only composed of the UPF. This is usually the most power-hungry NF in 5G networks since it is the one responsible for the actual routing and forwarding of data packets. Finally, the Access Network includes the part closest to the final user: the User Equipment (UE) and the base station (i.e., the antenna), which is called gNodeB. As shown in Figure 3, the UPF has three interfaces: N4 towards the SMF which is used to configure the PDU sessions and therefore involves control plane traffic, and N6 and N3 interfaces towards the Data Plane (DN) and the gNodeB, respectively, where the data plane traffic is sent.

Usually, being UPFs VMs or containers, they run on general-purpose servers. However, it is worth mentioning that different implementations (either relying on hardware or software acceleration devices/techniques) of UPF exist. In the literature, studies can be found comparing such implementations from a performance [16][16] point of view. The simplest UPF implementation corresponds to a user-space application. In order to increase the performance, accelerated UPFs exist; they exploit either software or hardware acceleration platforms/devices. Examples of the software ones leverage the eXpress Data Path (XDP) [17] and the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) technologies. XDP is a framework based on the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) technology that can run programs in a privileged context inside the system kernel; it enables the packet handling to bypass most of the operating system networking stack (e.g., context switches, interrupts, etc.). DPDK provides a poll mode driver that allows user-space applications to bypass the kernel and directly access dedicated network interfaces. Regarding the hardware accelerated UPFs, it is worth mentioning the P4 ones which have been studied in recent years [18].

In this paper, we focus on the simplest implementation of UPF: a user-space application running inside a container. Moreover, said container is deployed only through the use of Docker rather than the popular Container Orchestration and management platform, Kubernetes, to avoid having to use additional plugins (i.e., Multus [19][19]).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND SETUP

This section includes the setup of the conducted experiments (in Subsection IV.A) and their findings (in Subsection IV.B).

Figure 4. Details of the test setup as shown by the LoadCore dashboard. The NFs in the white boxes are provided by OAI, while the components encased in the blue and orange rectangle are simulated by LoadCore respectively by two different agents. As indicated by the red rectangle, the UPF is the system under test (SUT).

A. Experimental Setup

The full 5G network we used to conduct the experiments on the UPF is provided in Figure 4. Both the Control and User Plane are deployed using the OpenAir Interface (OAI) open-source implementation [20]. In detail, the Control Plane NFs are deployed on a Kubernetes Cluster, while the UPF is deployed as a Docker container on a server with the Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2680 v4 @ 2.40GHz. As shown in Figure 4, the Access Network and Data Plane are simulated by Loadcore [21] agents. Loadcore is a commercial 5G network simulator that makes use of “agents” to simulate a whole or only some components of a 5G network. The Loadcore agents are deployed as VMs on a different server than the one under test.

The power consumption and performance of the UPF will be evaluated in Subsection IV.B. In order to measure the former, a famous open-source power monitoring tool is installed: Scaphandre [22]. By relying on Intel RAPL (Running Average Power Limit) [23], Scaphandre provides the power measurements of both the whole server and of every single process running on it. The power measurements are then saved on the standard de facto open-source timeseries database: Prometheus [24].

Regarding the performance of the UPF, the latency of the data plane traffic is considered as the performance metric in this paper. This metric is natively provided by Loadcore.

The testing campaign involved five tests stressing the UPF while changing the C_x state statuses of each CPU of the server hosting the UPF. Each test was conducted with a different amount of C_x states enabled. Initially, only the active (i.e., C_0) state is enabled, then, progressively, the “sleeping” states are enabled. Therefore, in the last test all the C_x (i.e., $\{C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3, C_6\}$) can be assumed by every CPU of the hosting server. The enable/disable operation is carried out by a bash script that modifies the contents of the following folders: `/sys/devices/system/cpu/cpux/cpuidle/statex`.

In each test, a single UE is attaching to the network and creating a single PDU session. The offered load rate in downlink and uplink ranges from 10 kbit/s up to 100Mbit/s with a 10-kbit/s step. The payload size is kept equal to 1250 bytes and only the packet rate is changed. For each rate, a test is conducted for a 5-minute duration followed by a 2-minute pause.

B. Experimental Results

As mentioned before, results concerning the power and performance of the UPF will be presented in the following.

In Figures 5 and 6 the UPF power consumption (in Watts) is shown. As can be noticed by looking at their x axes, the results obtained during the test campaigns are split into two graphs for the sake of representing them with the appropriate scale to have a better visual representation. Hence, in both graphs there are five power plots, one for each C_x states configuration of the physical server, and the secondary vertical axis represents the offered load (i.e., the traffic rate generated in downlink and uplink). It is worth highlighting that in Figure 5 (i.e., for lower offered loads), the power plots are very noisy and often reach 0 (especially in the 10 kbit/s case). This happens since, in order to obtain the correct offered load while keeping the payload size constant (equal to 1250 bytes), the packet rate is low; therefore, the UPF waits until its buffer is full enough before processing the packets.

Focusing now on the less noisy Figure 6, we can examine the power savings when deeper C_x states are enabled. This is clearly shown by the test with the highest offered load (e.g., 100 Mbit/s), where the power is much lower in the purple plot (i.e., all C_x enabled) compared to the other ones. Moreover, the more C_x states are enabled, the lower the power, except for the combinations $\{C_0, C_1\}$ and $\{C_0, C_1, C_{1E}\}$; this is due to the fact that the C_{1E} is only a slightly enhanced version of C_1 . However, focusing on the power plots with 10 Mbit/s as offered load, we can notice that the deepest state (i.e., C_6) causes only a tiny saving with respect to the active state and causes a higher power consumption than the other combinations. Therefore, for lower offered loads, the power needed to transition from C_0 and C_6 (and vice versa) hinders the expected savings.

In Table 1, the average UPF power consumption is reported. Again, it is worth noticing that, in the 100 Mbit/s scenario, enabling all the C_x states allows to save more than half of the power with respect to the always active (i.e., C_0) case. For other offered load, it is worth highlighting that enabling C_6 results in a higher power compared to the other C_x state combinations.

So far, results show (for the most part) that, as the enabled C_x states deepen, the UPF power consumption decreases. However, this is not straightforward since we act on the

Figure 5. Power consumption of the UPF for offered loads ranging from 10 kbit/s up to 1 Mbit/s. Five power plots are shown: each one corresponds to a different combination of C_x states enabled.

Figure 6. Power consumption of the UPF for offered loads equal to 10 and 100 Mbit/s. Five power plots are shown: each one corresponds to a different combination of C_x states enabled.

Table 1. Average power consumption (in Watts) of the UPF for the different offered loads and C_x state combinations.

Offered Load [kbit/s]	C_0	C_0, C_1	C_0, C_1, C_{1E}	C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3	$C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3, C_6$
10	0.0004	0.00020	0.00020	0.00013	0.00013
100	0.0025	0.00116	0.00128	0.00086	0.00107
1000	0.0184	0.00882	0.00916	0.00770	0.01117
10000	0.1692	0.08566	0.08663	0.10515	0.14981
100000	1.7025	0.85920	0.86945	0.80076	0.67467

Table 2. Average power consumption (in Watts) of the hosting server for the different offered loads and C_x state combinations. The first row provides the average power consumption for the pauses between each test.

Offered Load [kbit/s]	C_0	C_0, C_1	C_0, C_1, C_{1E}	C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3	$C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3, C_6$
0	203.91	67.18	69.03	36.26	31.75
10	199.35	68.56	67.15	37.40	31.34
100	203.63	67.19	67.17	37.15	31.48
1000	202.78	67.31	67.24	38.36	33.90
10000	206.70	67.92	68.22	53.58	48.88
100000	208.41	70.18	70.26	64.66	54.66

hosting server rather than on the UPF container directly. As shown in Table 2, the power consumption of the hosting server decreases from left to right (e.g., from C_0 to $\{C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3, C_6\}$) and from top to bottom (e.g., from lowest to highest offered loads). However, since Scaphandre divides the total power of the server among the single processes based on their CPU usage, this explains how the change in host power is reflected onto the one ascribable to the UPF.

Finally, the results regarding the UPF performance are shown in Table 3, which reports the average latency percentage of packets in the different C_x state combinations. We can notice that no packets are lost in any scenario; thus, the UPF, in any C_x state-enabled scenario, would be able to route and forward mobile traffic without any drawbacks regarding the performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Environmental sustainability and in particular energy efficiency will be a crucial feature for the next mobile network generations (B5G and 6G). Therefore, in this paper, we have examined power management techniques to minimize the power consumption while not neglecting performance of the most power-hungry 5G NF: the UPF.

A classical power management technique has been used herein: the low power idle. It allows power saving caused by putting the CPU to “sleep” when not in use (when no packets are coming/being processed).

Tests were performed with different C_x (i.e., “sleeping”) state combinations. The UPF was stressed by one UE continuously sending and receiving traffic with a varying rate. The testing environment was realized with a blend of open-source (for the 5G NFs and the monitoring stack) and commercial (for the Access Network and DN) solutions.

Table 3. Packet latency (in %) for the different C_x state combinations, averaged over the five offered loads tested.

Latency	C_0	C_0, C_1	C_0, C_1, C_{1E}	C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3	$C_0, C_1, C_{1E}, C_3, C_6$
0us - 125us	99.75	99.57	99.42	99.45	99.41
125us - 250us	0.16	0.16	0.25	0.20	0.20
250us - 500us	0.05	0.25	0.27	0.29	0.29
500us - 1ms	0.03	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.07
1ms - 5ms	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03
5ms - 10ms	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10ms - 15ms	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
15ms - 20ms	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20ms - infinite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Results show that, in most cases the deeper C_x states are enabled, the more power is saved. This is especially true in the 100 Mbit/s scenario in which the power is more than halved as a result. However, results show that special care should be devoted to the enabling/disabling of the “deepest” C_x state (C_6) since the transitions from it to the active state (C_0) (and vice versa) actually hinder the power savings. Finally, the performance (as in latency) has been also evaluated. Results show no packet losses and no significant degradation. Thus, in all scenarios, mobile traffic can be supported without issue.

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